

DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AND DIPOLE MOMENT OF HYDROGEN HALIDES

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The dipole moments of hydrogen halides in solid and liquid state and in solutions in various polar and non-polar solvents have been calculated by applying the new equation. Unlike the Debye's values the new moments are in agreement with the gas values. The moments are independent of solvent and temperature. The ionic character of hydrogen halides is an inverse function of the square of the internuclear distance.

The success of Debye-Clausius-Mosotti (D.C.M.) equation (*Physikal. Z.*, 1912, 13, 97) showing the relationship between the dielectric constant and dipole moment in the case of gases and dilute solutions in non-polar solvents is not reflected in its application to the case of concentrated solutions in both non-polar and polar solvents and to normal and associated liquids. In dilute solutions the solvation has vitiated the results. No equation has so far been proposed to explain the high dielectric constant of associated liquids, rotating solids and solutions in polar solvents.

The equations put forth are summarised below :

(1) D.C.M. (*loc. cit.*).

$$(\epsilon - 1) \frac{M}{d} = \frac{4\pi N}{3} \times (\epsilon + 2) \left(\alpha + \frac{\mu^2}{3kT} \right) \text{ for liquids and solutions.}$$

$$(\epsilon - 1) \frac{M}{d} = 4\pi N \left(\alpha + \frac{\mu^2}{3kT} \right) \text{ for gases } \epsilon \approx 1$$

therefore $(\epsilon - n^2) \frac{M}{d} = \frac{4\pi N \mu^2}{3kT}$ for gases.

(2) Pauli (*Z. Physik*, 1921, 6, 219).

$$(\epsilon - n^2) \frac{M}{d} = N \left(\frac{C\mu^2}{kT} + \alpha \right)$$

(3) Onsager (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1486).

$$(\epsilon - n^2) \frac{M}{d} = \frac{4\pi N \mu^2}{9kT} \times \frac{\epsilon(n^2 + 2)^2}{2\epsilon + n^2}$$

(4) Kirkwood (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1939, 7, 94).

$$(\epsilon - n^2) \frac{M}{d} = \frac{g}{2} \times \frac{(n^2 + 2)^2}{3} \times \frac{1}{1 + \frac{n^2}{2\epsilon}} \times gB$$

$$\left(B = \frac{4\pi N \mu^2}{9kT}; g = \text{constant} \right)$$

(5) Frölich and Sack (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1944, A, 182, 388).

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\epsilon - n^2) \frac{M}{d} &= \frac{4\pi N \mu^2}{a^2 kT} \times \frac{3\epsilon}{2\epsilon + n^2} \times (1 + \gamma/2) \\
 &= \frac{4\pi N \mu^2}{3kT} \times \frac{3\epsilon}{2\epsilon + n^2} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\epsilon - n^2}{n^2} \right)^2 \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

(6) Jatkár (*Nature*, 1944, 153, 224).

$$(\epsilon - n^2) \frac{M}{d} = \frac{4\pi N \mu^2}{3kT} \frac{j+1}{j} \quad (j = \frac{1}{2} \text{ for liquids \& solids and } j = \infty \text{ for gases}).$$

Böttcher (*Physica*, 1939, 6, 50) has published numerous papers showing the applicability of Onsager's equation to the dielectric constant of pure liquids. Wilson (*Chem. Rev.*, 1939, 25, 377) has adversely criticised Onsager's equation as theoretically surprising and probably fortuitous in agreement.

Frölich and Sack (*loc. cit.*) have stated that for liquids with low viscosity there are no deviations from Onsager's theory which unfortunately is not the case because the dielectric constants of ethyl ether, chloroform, acetone and so on do not follow Onsager's equation.

In a series of papers published by Jatkár (*loc. cit.*) and Jatkár *et al.* (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1946, 28A, Part II; 1947, 30A, Part IV; *Indian J. Phys.*, 1948, 22, 431; 453; 1949, 23, 145; *Curr. Sci.*, 1949, 18, 76, 130) a remarkably simple relationship between the dielectric constant and dipole moment of liquids has been derived on the basis of assumptions inherent in previous theories.

The new equation is derived on the basis that a dipole is needle-shaped and that it has two possible settings in the electrical field, one parallel and another antiparallel to the direction of the field owing to the hindered rotation in liquids and solids. Since $2j+1$ is the total number of positions, $2j+1=2$ or $j=1/2$ for liquids and solids.

It is obvious that no simple single relationship can be postulated to take into account the complex nature of liquids.

In the present paper we have shown the application of the new equation to the dielectric constants of hydrogen halides in solid, liquid and solutions by applying both the Debye and the Onsager equations.

The dipole moments of hydrogen halides have formed the subject of numerous researches. Dielectric polarisations of HCl, HBr and HI have been measured by Fairbrother in different polar and non-polar solvents and the moments are calculated by applying the D.C.M. equation. The measurements by Fairbrother (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1541, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, 30, 388) in non-polar solvents like benzene, carbon tetrachloride, etc., exhibit a positive solvent effect. In ethyl bromide and ethylene dichloride, however, practically normal values (1.02D and 0.97D) were obtained for the moment of HCl. Recently Weith *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 805) have confirmed the positive solvent effect for HCl and HBr. The higher moments obtained in solutions have been

attributed to the increase of the electron density at the halogen end of the molecule, and in dioxane solutions there is an incipient ionisation of these solutes.

Smyth and Hitchcock (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 1831) have studied the dielectric constant of pure hydrogen halides at low temperatures in solid state, and Glockler and Peak (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1936, **4**, 659) have measured the values for pure liquid HCl. The dielectric constant-temperature curves show that there is a rotation in solid state, which is confirmed by the study of specific heats.

It is not possible to calculate the moment of pure solids and liquids with the help of Debye's equation. The application of Onsager's equation to the dielectric constant of pure hydrogen halides would be interesting in as much as these compounds correspond to the model of a sphere. While the Onsager's moment for liquid HCl is 1.07, the value for liquid HBr is 0.90 which is too high. A simple and straightforward explanation of all high dielectric constants of liquids and solids is given by the new relationship found by Jatkar (*loc. cit.*) between the dielectric constant of liquids and solids and the dipole moment of free molecules.

The authors have calculated the moments of halogen hydrides in solid and liquid state and also in solutions by applying the new and simple relationship,

$$P = (\epsilon - 1)M/d; P_s = (\pi^2 - 1)M/d; P - P_s = 4\pi N\mu^2/kT$$

for pure solids and liquids, and

$$P_{12} = (\epsilon_{12} - 1) \frac{M_1 f_1 + M_2 f_2}{d_{12}} = P_1 f_1 + P_2 f_2 \text{ and}$$

$$P_s - P_s = 4\pi N\mu^2/kT \text{ for solutions.}$$

Hydrogen Fluoride

The high dielectric constant of liquid HF (174.3 at -73° and 83.6 at 0°) cannot be explained on the basis of the Hexamer structure of HF at low temperature unless one adopts the proton transition theory, the hydrogen oscillating between two fluorine atoms. On the other hand, if one postulates a high degree of flexibility of HF held by hydrogen bonds, the rotation will be of hindered type and there should exist a transition temperature for the liquid as in the case of other hydrogen bonded liquids like methyl alcohol, water, etc. Using a modified equation

$$(\epsilon - \pi^2) M/d = 4\pi N\mu^2/k(T - \theta)$$

a value of -120°C for θ would yield 1.88 as the dipole moment in liquid HF as compared to the value of 1.91 for the gas (cf. Smyth and Hanney, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 171). According to Weith's measurements the electric moments of HF are 1.9, 2.0, 2.2 and 2.34 in C_6H_6 , CCl_4 , $n\text{-C}_7\text{H}_{16}$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$. Unfortunately no data are available to enable a recalculation of these results.

Electronic Polarisation.—The new value of electronic polarisation $P_s = (\pi^2 - 1)M/d$ is calculated from the refractive index and density data given by Smyth (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1912, **A**, 87, 336) and assumed to be independent of temperature.

TABLE I

Substance.	Temp.	Density.	Ref. index.	P_1 .
HCl	10.5°	0.854	1.254	24.5
HBr	10.0°	1.630	1.325	37.5
HI	12.0°	2.270	1.466	64.8

The results are given in the following tables.

TABLE II

Dielectric constant and dipole moments of hydrogen halides.

(Pure liquids and solids).

Substance.	$t^\circ(\text{C})$.	ϵ .	P .	$\mu \times 10^{18}$.
HCl (solid) (a)	-173°	17.25	415.6	0.83
	-143	15.38	366.9	0.89
	-117	14.53	345.3	0.94
HCl (liquid) (b)	-112	14.05	375.2	1.00
	-66.5	8.92	253.0	0.91
	-15.0	6.33	198.0	0.90
HBr (solid) (a)	-165.5	11.86	358.74	0.78
	-140.5	8.45	246.09	0.70
	-124.8	8.30	241.14	0.73
HBr (liquid) (a)	-87.5	8.48	247.08	0.83
	-85.0	7.00	218.50	0.76
	-70.0	6.40	202.10	0.77
HI (solid) (a)	-143.0	4.50	144.8	0.43
	-117.0	4.20	133.3	0.44
	-85.0	3.96	124.2	0.45
HI (liquid) (a)	-53.0	3.87	120.2	0.47
	-50.0	3.38	106.6	0.42
	-37.0	3.27	103.5	0.40

(a) Smyth and Hitchcock, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 1831.

(b) Glockler and Peak, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1936, 4, 659.

TABLE III

Dipole moments of hydrogen halides in various solvents.

Solvent.	t° .	f_2 .	ϵ .	d .	P_1 .	$\mu \times 10^{18}$.
			(1) HCl.			
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{Cl}$	25°	0.0069	2.288	0.8733	237.39	1.06
		0.0203	2.317	0.8742	236.26	1.06
		0.0302	2.339	0.8746	237.50	1.06
CCl_4 (c)	25°	0.0026	2.232	1.5815	291.92	(1.10)
		0.0107	2.247	1.5811	244.02	1.07
C_6H_6 (c)	25°	0.0039	2.018	0.7737	223.33	1.01
		0.0101	2.028	0.7740	215.65	1.00

TABLE III (contd.)

Solvent.	t° .	f_2 .	ϵ .	d .	P_1 .	$\mu \times 10^{18}$.
$C_2H_5Cl_2$ (d)	20°	0.0246	10.561	1.2521	237.51	1.05
		0.0194	10.571	1.2528	252.58	1.08
		0.0167	10.580	1.2533	240.31	(1.15)
(2) HBr						
C_6H_6 (e)	20°	0.0489	2.342	0.9040	158.65	0.79
		0.0407	2.334	0.8996	157.15	0.78
		0.0221	2.310	0.8899	164.45	0.81
CCl_4 (e)	20°	0.0346	2.266	1.5982	136.29	0.71
		0.0154	2.250	1.5958	142.09	0.73
		0.0102	2.246	1.5951	145.95	0.73
(3) HI						
C_6H_6 (e)	20°	0.0654	2.307	0.9435	94.86	0.40
		0.0370	2.297	0.9153	95.25	0.41
		0.0244	2.294	0.9028	99.92	0.43
CCl_4 (e)	20°	0.0459	2.246	1.6156	85.64	0.33
		0.04231	2.245	1.6142	84.14	0.32
		0.02692	2.242	1.6069	84.58	0.32

(c) Fairbrother, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 43.(d) Fairbrother, *ibid.*, 1933, 1541.(e) Fairbrother, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, 30, 862.

TABLE IV

Solvent.	D.C.M.(1) (sol)	$\mu \times 10^{18}$		Gas D.C.M.(1)	Solvent.	D.C.M.(1) (sol)	$\mu \times 10^{18}$		Gas D.C.M.(1)
		New.	Onsager.				New.	Onsager.	
(1) HCl					(2) HBr				
Pure solid	—	0.90	—	—	Pure solid	—	0.79	—	—
Liquid	—	0.99	1.07	1.03	Pure liquid	—	0.76	0.90	0.78
C_6H_6	1.26	1.06	—	1.06	C_6H_6	1.00	0.79	—	—
CCl_4	1.32	1.07	—	—	CCl_4	0.96	0.72	—	—
C_6H_{12}	1.32	1.01	—	—	(3) HI				
$C_2H_5Cl_2$	0.97	1.10	—	—	Pure solid	—	0.44	—	—
—	—	—	—	—	Pure liquid	—	0.40	—	0.38
—	—	—	—	—	C_6H_6	0.58	0.41	—	—
—	—	—	—	—	CCl_4	0.50	0.33	—	—

D.C.M. equation (1).

DISCUSSION

The density of solid hydrogen halides is not known at low temperatures, specially near the transition temperature where large changes in density take place. The authors have taken the density at melting point for the purpose of calculation. Hence the results, specially for solids near the transition point, are not as satisfactory as could

be expected. It is very remarkable that the moments calculated in solid and liquid state and solutions by applying the new equation are nearly the same as those for gases, except the moment of HCl calculated from the data in ethyl bromide (1.4 D). The moments are independent of temperatures and solvents.

The higher values in solution reported in literature are thus due to the application of D.C.M. equation and the explanations of higher moments in solution advanced by Fairbrother are unnecessary. In the case of solutions in non-polar solvents ($\epsilon \approx 2.5$) it can be shown (Jatkar *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, 1947) that $\mu_{D.C.M.} / \mu_{NEW} > 1.4$ when $P_{2\infty D.C.M.} > P_2 (D.C.M.)$. The so-called solvent effect in the case of hydrogen halides is due to this factor. If the solvent is polar (*i.e.* $\epsilon > 2.5$) then the ratio $\mu_{D.C.M.} / \mu_{NEW}$ is less than 1.4.

The ionic natures as calculated from the dipole moment data $i = \mu/e.d.$ are 0.43, 0.17, 0.11 and 0.05 for HF, HCl, HBr and HI. The present authors (Jatkar *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, 1949) have pointed out a simple relationship between the ionic nature and the internuclear charges, $i = (Z_A / Z_A + Z_B) n$, where Z_A and Z_B are the nuclear charges of the atoms A and B and n is a constant which is 8/3 in the case of hydrogen halides.

TABLE V

Bond.	Distance.	$Z_A / Z_A + Z_B$.	n .	Ionic Calc. ($Z_A / Z_A + Z_B$) n .	ionic nature Obs. $\mu/e.d.$
HF	0.92	0.100	8/3	0.27	0.43
HCl	1.28	0.056	8/3	0.15	0.17
HBr	1.43	0.028	8/3	0.074	0.11
HI	1.63	0.018	8/3	0.049	0.052

The calculated ionic nature of HF, while in agreement with the bond energy data (Jatkar and Kulkarni, *Curr. Sci.*, 1949, 18, 131) is lower than the observed value 0.43. It is interesting to point out the inverse relationship between the ionic nature and the square of the internuclear distance in the case of HF, HCl, HBr and HI.